

COOPERATIVE COMMUNICATIONS COMBINATION DIVERSITY TECHNIQUES AND OPTIMAL POWER ALLOCATION EXPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

The main task of this article is to focus on the performance of cooperative MIMO relaying in terms of data rate and Power. Furthermore, compare these performances when using Maximum Ratio Combining (MRC) and equal gain combining (EGC).The average SNR improvement of MRC is typically about 5 dB better than with EGC and direct link.The preciseness of the derived closed form expression of optimum power allocation of the DF-based relaying system is demonstrated by simulation results.

KEY WORDS

Cooperative Communication, Amplify and forward, Decode and forward, optimum power allocation

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea of cooperative communication for wireless networks can be traced back to utilize of the relay channel. *Cover and El Gamal* [1], studied a three-node network with a source, a destination and a relay on the information theoretic properties. By the use of an additional relay node the network capacity was well observed and three theorems were established. With the current growth in cellular networks, sensor networks, and wireless ad hoc networks, the opinion of cooperative communication has attracted tremendous attention. However, recent studies generally focus on the diversity, spectral efficiency and power efficiency achieved by cooperative transmission to combat channel fading instead of the information theoretic perspective. Furthermore, with higher demand on the size of handset and sensors, current research develops a scenario where single-antenna mobiles share their antennas in a virtual multiple-antenna system. Each node could perform both as a source or a relay of other nodes which are symmetrical to each other as shown in Fig.1

Fig.1: Symmetrical Transmission System

The two different emphases in recent work make cooperative communication and networking a promising technology with significant capacity and multiplexing gain increase in wireless networks. Although a number of researchers demonstrated the understanding of different cooperative communication schemes in recent years, many more issues such as the cooperative system architecture, outage probability, optimization, resource allocation, cross-layer design are open to discuss to make these techniques practical and effective. In this paper, we consider a three-node scenario consisting of one source, one relay and one destination which is the simplest form in cooperative system as in fig-2.

Speedy, stable and good quality communication is significant in the information age. Citizens want improved voice or video quality, wider coverage while smaller and more power and bandwidth efficient handsets from every corner in the world. Overcoming the effects of fading, outages, and circuit failures is always a large alarm in wireless communications contrast to fiber, cable and other medium transmissions. One solution is to use send out diversity where identical information-bearing signals are transmitted from independent sources through independent channels. The more independent the fading characteristics between channels the more diversity gain are achieved at the receiver. Transmit diversity is practical, effective and economical in mitigating multipath fading compared with other techniques such as transmitter power control, time and frequency diversity and receive diversity approaches [2].

A number of schemes for transmit diversity are recommended in cellular systems. Coding, time and frequency are employed by the transmitters to produce diversity gain [2], [3]. Although the pro of transmit diversity on a cellular base station is evident, it may not apply for other approaches where the system cannot support various transmit antennas due to size, charge, or hardware restriction.

To overcome this obstacle cooperative transmission is proposed. The technique allows a only one antenna user to gain diversity similar to conventional transmit diversity systems to conflict slow fading. The essential structure block in cooperative systems is the relay channel, whereby a source transmits a message to object (destination) with the aid of a relay. Thus, the destination receives two messages with the equivalent source but through independent fading channels. By joining these signals with combination techniques like a MRC or EGC, the diversity gain can be obtained without using additional antennas, power or bandwidths, and thus cost-effective[4]. Our purpose is to quantify the advantages of using cooperative transmissions in expand the network lifetime of the energy-constrained wireless network [5].

The reset of this article is arranged as follow: section-2 provides the general description of signaling method of cooperative communication. The system model is presented in section-3. In section-4 the power allocation methods are provided. The system simulation and results are presented in section-5.

2. RECENT COOPERATIVE SIGNALING SCHEMES

In the essential category of cooperative transmission, the whole transmission time can be separated into two time slots. In the initial/first time slot, the source transmits a signal to the relay and the source. In the second time slot, the relay makes a decision, how to reply to the received signal. Numerous cooperative signaling methods are developed with diverse signal processing strategies at the relay [6-8].

i .Decode-and-forward

In the decode-and-forward (DF) mode, the relay decodes, re-encodes and retransmits the full information to provide the destination edition of identical information-bearing signal as the source to achieve the second order diversity. This signaling is similar to the traditional sense of a relay channel and has the adaptability to channel conditions. However, when the detection by the relay is failed, the information from the relay channel will be harmful to the detection at the destination, which is called error propagation.

ii. Amplify-and-forward

Another straightforward cooperative technique is the amplify-and-forward (AF) relaying. In this method the relay simply amplifies and forwards the noisy version of the signal transmitted by the source. Interestingly, it has been shown in [9] that by optimally combining the signals received from the source and relay with the necessary CSI available at the destination, this method achieves second order diversity, which is full diversity for the two-user case. Amplify-and-forward does not require the relay to decode the source's transmission, which is a major advantage over decode-and-forward. *Souryal* in [10] proposed a new hybrid AF/DF relaying protocol in which the relay uses CRC to detects whether the decoding is successful. If so, it re-encodes and transmits the message as in the fixed DF method.

3. SYSTEM MODEL

A source *node-A* transmits information to the destination *node-B* with the help of a relay node *R* as shown in Fig.2. For the transmission, time division multiplexing is assumed, in the first time slot the source broadcasts the information to both relay and destination. In the second time slot the relay decodes and forwards the received information to the destination. At the destination, the signal from the relay path and the direct path are combined to reduce the fading of the resultant signal. Hard-decision-decoding is processed for any decoding process.

Fig.2: System Model

The two stages of the transmission process are:

Stage-1: The signal received at destination from the source is given by: (i.e, direct link)

$$y_D = \sqrt{P_s} h_{sd} (x) + n_{sd} \quad (1)$$

y is the received symbol, P_s is the Power at the transmitter, h is complex scaling factor corresponding to Rayleigh multipath channel, x is the transmitted symbol (taking values +1's and -1's) and n is the Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). The noise n has the Gaussian probability density function with $p(n) = \left(1/\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}\right) e^{-\frac{(n-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$ with zero mean ($\mu = 0$) and σ^2 as its variance.

The channel h is known at the receiver and Equalization is performed at the receiver by dividing the received symbol y by the *a priori* known channel

$$\hat{y}_D = \frac{\sqrt{P_s} h_{SD} x + n_{SD}}{\sqrt{P_s} h_{SD}} = x + \frac{n_{SD}}{\sqrt{P_s} h_{SD}} = x + \hat{n} \quad (2)$$

Where $\hat{n}$ is the additive noise scaled by the channel coefficient.

Stage-2: The signal received at the relay from the source is given as:

$$y_r = \sqrt{P_s} h_{sr} x_s + n_r \quad (3)$$

The equation of y_r is equalized at the relay to generate a new signal $\rightarrow x_s + n_r/\sqrt{P_s} h_{sr}$

Stage-3: This signal is sent by relay to the destination, the received signal by:

$$y_D = \sqrt{P_R} \cdot h_{SR} \cdot \underbrace{\left(x_S + \frac{n_R}{\sqrt{P_S} \cdot h_{SR}}\right)}_{\text{Relay_Signal}} + n_D \quad (4)$$

With the SNR given by:

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{P_R \cdot h_{RD}^2}{\sigma^2 \left(1 + \frac{P_R \cdot h_{RD}^2}{P_S \cdot h_{SR}^2}\right)} \quad (5)$$

As the source broadcasts the signal in the first time slot, the signal from the direct path is also received at the destination with the SNR equal to $\gamma_2 = P_S \cdot h_{SD}^2 / \sigma^2$. We assume that full CSI at both paths is available at the destination, so coherent combining is possible in such way the overall SNR at the destination can be written as $\gamma_D = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2$

$$\gamma_D = \underbrace{\frac{P_S \cdot h_{SD}^2}{\sigma^2}}_{\gamma_1} + \underbrace{\frac{P_R \cdot h_{RD}^2}{\sigma^2 \left(1 + \frac{P_R \cdot h_{RD}^2}{P_S \cdot h_{SR}^2}\right)}}_{\gamma_2} \quad (6)$$

4. POWER ALLOCATION METHOD

This section provides the formulation problem which will be examined through simulation studies. We consider the approach of a system in which individual node has upper bound of energy (i.e. limited power wireless terminals).

$$P_T = P_S + P_R \quad (7)$$

Where P_S is the Power allocated to the source and P_R the relay Power.

These workstations works in network of cellular type or works in unlicensed band (To prevent interfering with other networks in the same band, the total power radiated by network in this band should not exceed a specified level/threshold). Such types of network have upper limitation on total power transmission. So transmitted power by *source* is given by:

$$P_S = \lambda P_T, \quad 0 < \lambda < 1 \quad (8)$$

Transmitted power by supporting *relay* is given by $P_r = (1 - \lambda)P_T$.

Ergodic capacity for cooperative communication is given as $C = \frac{1}{2} B \cdot \log_2(1 + \gamma_D)$. In the equation, the right hand side is multiplied by a factor of 1/2, this is due to the fact that proposed system model works in two time slots and utilize only half channel degree of freedom.

4.1 Optimum Power Allocation

This is a centralized power allocation method in which source should have full information knowledge or CSI between all nodes prior to transmission. In practice, the channels are estimated by sending guidance sequence before the actual message transmission, when each node operates in time mode or with TDMA technique. When the source transmits the training bits, relay node can simultaneously estimate their source-to-relay CSI due to the broadcast nature of the wireless medium. Similarly, when relay (R) transmits the training bits, the CSI of source-to-relay and relay-to-destination can be estimated at the source and destination respectively (we assume that forward and backward channels between the relay and destination are the same due to reciprocity). These transmissions occur on the same frequency band and same coherence interval. However, CSI of relay-to-destination can be obtainable at the source only through channel feedback.

In a slow fading setting, frequent training is not necessary. Hence, in this case, we can neglect training period as compared to actual data transmission period. On the basis of CSI, S distributes the available power (P_T) between S and R. So our main objective is efficiently utilizing the available power to improve γ_D at destination. Maximizing the equation of γ_D can be written as:

$$\max_{P_R, P_S} \gamma_D = \frac{P_S h_{SD}^2}{\sigma^2} + \frac{P_R h_{RD}^2}{\sigma^2 (1 + \frac{P_R h_{RD}^2}{P_S h_{SR}^2})} \quad (9)$$

subject to $P_T = P_S + P_R$

Via *Lagrange multiplier* maximization scenario, the modified objective function can be written as

$$j = \frac{P_S h_{SD}^2}{\sigma^2} + \frac{P_R h_{RD}^2}{\sigma^2 (1 + \frac{P_R h_{RD}^2}{P_S h_{SR}^2})} - \lambda (P_R + P_S - P_T) \quad (10)$$

Here λ is a constant. Taking partial derivative of j with respect to P_S , P_R , and λ equated to zero gives optimal solution for P_S and P_R .

Then, optimal solution for P_S and P_R can be given as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_S &= \left(\frac{W}{Q} - \left[\frac{W^2}{Q^2} - \frac{N}{Q} \right]^{1/2} \right) P_T \\ P_R &= \left(1 - \left[\frac{W}{Q} - \left[\frac{W^2}{Q^2} - \frac{N}{Q} \right]^{1/2} \right] \right) P_T \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

where,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} N &= h_{RD}^2 (h_{SD}^2 + h_{SR}^2) \\ W &= h_{RD}^2 \left[N - h_{SR}^2 h_{SD}^2 \right] \\ Q &= h_{RD}^2 N - h_{SR}^2 \left[(h_{SD}^2 - h_{RD}^2) h_{SR}^2 - 2h_{RD}^2 h_{SD}^2 \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

5. SIMULATION ANALYSIS RESULTS

The simulation analysis conveys BER and power allocation. To evaluate the true performance of the proposed scheme, computer simulation is conducted. The results confirm the advantages and disadvantages of the proposed mathematical expression through the following analysis of the bit error rate (BER) curves.

Cooperation between nodes can have a mutual positive pro for both nodes. However, there are cases where only one of the partners takes all the advantages of cooperation. Hence, it would be of attention to examine and estimate the mutual outlook of cooperation and explore its benefits to each of the partners. The purpose would be to see when it is useful for nodes to cooperate and when it is not. For a given total power, we have analyzed and provided regions (between source-relay and relay-destination) in which cooperation enhances the performance. Suppose that propagation attenuation exponent is 4. We fix the location of the source and the destination node and analyze regions where cooperation can be useful and the quantity of improvement that can be achieved when two nodes are assisting.

In all the simulation it's assumed that the variance of the noise is unit (i.e. $N_o = 1$), White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) and Rayleigh Channel. Where the decoding process used is called equalization, this led to a full knowledge of the CSI.

Fig.3 compares the BER versus the SNR for our theoretical analysis when Maximum Ratio Combining (MRC) and Equal Gain Combining (EGC) are considered at the destination. For both channels, BPSK modulation is considered; equalization and hard-decision-decoding are performed at any receiver as the decoding process.

Fig.3: BER versus SNR for EGC, MRC

Fig.3 shows that cooperative communication allows single antenna users to gain diversity similar as in conventional transmits diversity systems to combat slow fading. By combining the signals from both relayed and direct path with combination techniques like a MRC or an EGC, the diversity gain can be obtained without using extra antennas, power or bandwidths, and thus a cost-effective solution. As both EGC and MRC achieve the same asymptotic diversity, it is clear that EGC, which does not need channel gain information, offers a superior tradeoff between difficulty and performance.

From Fig. 3, we notice that MRC outperforms the EGC for this decoding technique when the average SNR less than 30 dB. The average SNR improvement of MRC is typically about 5 dB better than with EGC and direct link.

In Fig.4 and Fig.5, we simulate different ratios of P_s and P_r with two unlike total power available ($P_T=100dB$ and $P_T=300dB$). We can observe that, BER versus power distribution, under different total power constraints in the single relay node case, attain unique minima. Furthermore, it can be concluded that under different total power constraints, the optimal transmission power schemes are dissimilar. In case of the total transmission power is small; the BER is not very sensitive to the source and the relay power distribution. When the total transmission power is relatively larger, which means that the BER at the destination could be somewhat small, the BER performance is aware to the power distribution. The source should spend significantly more power than the relay. Alternatively, the relay should keep a lot of power. Although P_R is small, it provides cooperative diversity at the destination.

The ratio P_s/P_T gives thought on the relay position, we assume that a source node needs more power when the destination is getting far away from it (i.e., a node require extra power when extended transmission distance).

We can see that under different available power (in dB), the performance of the communication depends on the power allocated to both source and relay; because the less the BER, the less the noise will be. So we can expect a better communication link

When the power ratio P_s / P_T is less than 0.4 the relay is far away from the destination, more power needs to be allocated to it to assure that the transmission from relay to destination is successful. In case of the relay node in the middle position between the source and destination the power ration is between 0.5 and 0.6. The BER becomes lower and we can expect a better communication as the noise is reduced.

When the power ratio is greater than 0.6 the relay is far away from the source, the source needs more power to transmit the information to the relay. The BER gets higher, the noise power is increased. In this situation a reliable communication link may not be feasible. Furthermore, we observe that we have two situations: Whether the relay is closer to the source or destination and the situation where it's in the middle of them. In the first situation the power allocation is called Optimum Power Allocation method (OPA) and the other called Equal Power Allocation method (EPA).

Fig.4 and Fig.5 are illustrates that the OPA outperforms the EPA methods when the total power available is small. Their BER are almost the same when the power ratio is between 0.6 and 0.8 with a greater total power. When the power increase, the OPA method can really bring about BER performance improvement when the relay is close to the destination.

Fig.4: BER as a function of the source power ratio with PT=100dB

Fig.5: BER as a function of the source power ratio with $P_T=300\text{dB}$

6. CONCLUSION

We have presented in this paper a power allocation method and comparison of BER between EGC and MRC. By introducing cooperation protocol among nodes, both energy pro and location advantage can be explored such that the device lifetime is improved and diversity is achieved. First, decode-and-forward cooperation protocol is employed among nodes. We discuss at which position the node should cooperate and how much power should be allocated for cooperation. An optimization issue is formulated with an aim to maximize the SNR device lifetime under a total power constraint.

The cooperation scheme is proposed as follow: an optimum power should be given to the source according to the relay position; the relay regenerates the received signal by equalization and hard-decision-decoding and forwards it to the receiver which will do the same process to decode the information. The power given to the relay will also be optimized in order to get a reliable communication link.

It can be observed that the performance differs according to the total power available, and according to the combining technique used. The power allocation method is resumed into two methods; the OPA method and the EPA method. According to the position of the relay each one performs better than the other, better transmission link, long communication time may be expectable if the optimum method is chosen and may also be helpful for the resource management.

Future work may include solving the optimization in particular scenarios, development of a selective strategy to circumvent limitations due to link source-relay, extension to multi-hop transmission, in particular assessing how diversity can improve performances.

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